

Conferences as a Tool for Increasing Medical AI Literacy: A Before and After Study

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Abstract. This study looked at whether the NHS National AI Conference—held within the GIANT Health Event—helped improve AI literacy among NHS healthcare professionals. Attendees expressed baseline optimism about AI's potential to improve efficiency and patient outcomes. Using a before-and-after survey completed by 43 attendees, we found a positive trend in understanding, confidence, and a sense of empowerment to use AI in daily work. We highlight the need for further skills-based conferences as part of a standardised national AI curriculum.

Keywords: Medical AI, AI literacy, AI Curriculum, medical education, conference, AI, NHS.

1.1 Introduction

The United Kingdom's (UK) National Health Service (NHS) is globally recognised for its patient-centred care, but faces significant challenges. Declining productivity and a sharp rise in waiting times for procedures highlights a system under pressure, with human error contributing to avoidable mortality and escalating costs [1,2]. Artificial intelligence (AI) promises a potential solution to these issues. It has already shown potential in applications such as radiological reporting and clinical documentation [5,6], delivering improvements in accuracy, efficiency and affordability [5].

However, effective integration of medical AI depends on upskilling the workforce, with studies highlighting education as a significant barrier to adoption [7,8]. Gazquez-Garcia et al. identify five essential competencies for healthcare professionals: AI fundamentals, ethics, data analysis, communication, and evaluation [9]. In a report by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 72% of doctors acknowledged AI's transformative potential [10]. Even still, many remain hesitant due to a limited understanding of its risks and capabilities [11]. Practical training opportunities are constrained by a lack of funding, limited access to experts, and insufficient awareness. Conferences such as the Global Innovation and New Technology (GIANT) Health

conference offer a potential solution by fostering AI literacy and ethical awareness through education and networking [12].

1.2 Methods

We conducted a before-and-after study to assess the impact of conferences on NHS professionals' understanding of AI, with the aim of informing future AI education and curriculum development within the NHS. The cohort was primarily composed of healthcare professionals, 70% of whom worked directly in clinical roles, and the majority were attending their first AI-focused conference. Our survey measured self-reported knowledge and confidence regarding AI, including perceived risks and benefits, ethical concerns, and the role of AI in clinical empowerment. Responses measured using a standardised 5-point Likert scale underwent statistical analysis employing the non-parametric McNemar's test. R version 4.3.3 was used to conduct this analysis. The threshold for statistical significance was established at a p-value of less than 0.05.

1.3 Results

The survey was completed by 43 attendees, with clinical professionals making up the majority (53.49%). A significant proportion (65.12%) reported never having attended a similar conference before. Post-conference, there was an increase in self-reported understanding of AI, rising from 83.72% to 90.70% ($p = 0.248$). Awareness of AI's potential benefits also improved, increasing from 69.77% to 85.05% ($p = 0.070$). Confidence in using AI in practice increased from 53.49% to 69.77% ($p = 0.070$). The proportion of attendees who felt empowered to apply AI in their day-to-day work grew from 51.16% to 67.44% ($p = 0.070$). Furthermore, concern regarding the use of AI in healthcare decreased, with 65.12% expressing concern pre-conference compared to 53.49% post-conference ($p = 0.267$).

1.4 Conclusion

In conclusion, medical AI conferences may help to improve AI understanding among NHS healthcare professionals. Our findings demonstrated an increase in understanding of AI's benefits and a greater sense of empowerment to incorporate AI into daily practice. We highlight a baseline optimism towards medical AI, suggesting a receptive climate for further educational and integration efforts. We suggest that future conferences should be embedded within a national curriculum which standardises AI-related skills and knowledge across the NHS workforce. This should be supported by practical, skills-based learning opportunities, including interactive workshops that offer hands-on experience and promote critical evaluation of AI tools. Such initiatives should address concerns around ethics, transparency, and workload to build trust and further enhance AI literacy, thereby supporting safe and effective AI adoption across the NHS.

Ultimately, a standardised and accessible national AI curriculum, underpinned by robust governance and a supportive technological infrastructure is key to enabling a motivated workforce to deliver improved patient care throughout the health service.

Disclosure of Interests

The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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